

Complexes of Thiovanol with UO_2^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Pb^{2+} **

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Complex compounds of thiovanol with UO_2^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Pb^{2+} have been isolated. UO_2^{2+} forms a yellow coloured complex at pH 4.5 having 1 : 1 :: metal : ligand stoichiometry and an orange yellow coloured complex at pH 8.5 having 1 : 2 :: M : L. Zn^{2+} and Pb^{2+} form colourless complexes with thiovanol at pH 7.5-8.0 having 1 : 2 :: M : L stoichiometry. Infrared spectral studies on these complexes indicate that sulphhydryl (-SH) and primary alcoholic (-OH) groups are involved in coordination. These systems have also been pH-metrically studied. UO_2^{2+} forms only one complex in solution, Zn^{2+} and Pb^{2+} form complexes in solution having 1 : 2 :: M : L stoichiometry.

In continuation of the work¹⁻⁶ on transition metal complexes of thiovanol, the present paper describes the complexes of UO_2^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Pb^{2+} .

Materials and Methods

UO_2^{2+} gave two complexes with thiovanol at different pH values, one yellow coloured at pH 4.5 and another orange yellow coloured at pH 8.5. The isolation of the complexes are described below.

Chloromonothiovanalato triaquo Uranyl(VI) monohydrate, yellow $[UO_2(C_3H_7O_2S)Cl(H_2O)_3] \cdot H_2O$. To 25 ml 0.1M Uranyl nitrate solution (Analar grade) 200 ml 0.1M TV solution in water was added. On adding HCl the colour intensified and at pH 4.5 a yellow solid separated out after adding ethanol. It was washed with water, alcohol and finally with acetone and dried at 80°. The complex was insoluble in water and common organic solvents. M.P. 250°(d). The elemental analysis requires U = 49.1%, S = 6.6%, C = 7.4%, H = 3.0%, Cl = 7.3%; Found, U = 48.7%, C = 7.2%, H = 2.9%, Cl = 7.15%, S = 6.5%.

Diaquo bis(thiovanalato)Uranyl(VI) $[UO_2(C_3H_7O_2S)_2(H_2O)_2]$ Orange yellow. Thiovanol solution (225 ml 0.1 M) was added to an equimolar Uranyl nitrate solution (25 ml) and the pH was raised to 8.5 by adding sodium hydroxide solution. The colour of the solution changed from red to orange yellow. The solution was concentrated on a steam bath when an orange yellow solid separated out. It was washed with water, alcohol and finally with acetone and dried at 80°. The complex was insoluble in water and common organic solvents, Diaquo bis(thiovanalato)Uranyl(VI) requires U = 45.7%, S = 12.3%, C = 13.8%, H = 3.4%; Found U = 44.9%, S = 11.9%, C = 13.2%, H = 3.32%.

Zn-TV and Pb-TV Complexes : A white precipitate was obtained on adding excess of 0.1M thiovanol

(10 times) solution to an equimolar solution of lead nitrate (25 ml) pH 7.5. Similarly, in the case of Zinc, a white precipitate was obtained at pH 7.5-8.0. Both the precipitates were thoroughly washed with water alcohol and finally with acetone and dried at 60°. The complexes are insoluble in ordinary solvents and do not melt or decompose even at 350°. The complexes were analysed for the sulphur and metal contents. The results of analyses show a stoichiometry of 1 : 2. (TV = Thiovanol)

Infrared spectral studies : Infrared spectra on the complexes were recorded in KBr disc on a Perkin-Elmer model-221 in the region 4000 to 600 cm^{-1} . Infrared spectrum of the ligand was recorded neat. The bands of diagnostic value and their tentative assignments are given in table.

pH-metric studies :

pH-metric studies on the complexes in solution were made using Leeds and Northrup pH-meter in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The ionic strength of the solutions were kept constant by adding sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid. The solutions A, B and C were titrated against standard NaOH solution $\left(\frac{M}{100}\right)$.

For UO_2 -TV and Zn-TV Systems :

- (A) 5 ml $\frac{M}{100}$ $HClO_4$ + 2.5 ml $\frac{M}{25}$ $NaClO_4$ + 42.5 ml water.
- (B) 5 ml $\frac{M}{100}$ $HClO_4$ + 2.5 ml $\frac{M}{25}$ $NaClO_4$ + 25 ml $\frac{M}{111}$ TV + 17.5 ml water.

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Compound	Medium	ν_{SH} (cm^{-1})	δ_{OH} (cm^{-1})	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ (cm^{-1}) Secondary alcoholic	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ (cm^{-1}) Primary alcoholic	ν_{CS} (cm^{-1})
$\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{S}$	Neat	2560	1415	1080	1040	665
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{S}_2\text{Cl}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2)]\text{H}_2\text{O}$	KBr disc	—	1405	1080	1020	650
$[\text{UO}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{S}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	KBr disc	—	1400	1080	1010	655
Zn-TV (1 : 2)	„	—	1390	1080	1025	660
Pb-TV (1 : 2)	„	—	1405	1080	1015	655

(C) 5 ml $\frac{M}{100}$ HClO_4 + 2.5 ml $\frac{M}{25}$ NaClO_4 + 2.5 ml $\frac{M}{100}$ metals + 25 ml $\frac{M}{111}$ TV + 15 ml water.

Total volume 50 ml, *medium aqueous*.

For Pb-TV System : The following solutions were titrated against standard NaOH solution ($\frac{M}{10.6}$).

(A) 5 ml $\frac{M}{100}$ HClO_4 + 2 ml $\frac{M}{100}$ NaClO_4 + 33 ml water.

(B) 5 ml $\frac{M}{100}$ HClO_4 + 2 ml $\frac{M}{100}$ NaClO_4 + 0.5 ml $\frac{M}{10}$ TV + 32.5 ml water.

(C) 5 ml $\frac{M}{100}$ HClO_4 + 2 ml $\frac{M}{100}$ NaClO_4 + 0.5 ml $\frac{M}{10}$ -TV + 5 ml $\frac{M}{100}$ metal ion + 27 ml water.

Total volume 40 ml *medium aqueous*.

Discussion

The plots of pH versus the volume of alkali added gave S-shaped curves. The difference between the volumes of alkali corresponding to the inflection points of the curves obtained for solutions (B) and (C) shows the volume of alkali required for neutralization of hydrogen ion replaced by the metal ion from the ligand molecule. Making use of this information the composition of Zn-TV and Pb-TV complexes were found to be 1 : 2 :: metal : ligand and 1 : 1 : M :: L in case of UO_2^{2+} -TV.

A comparison of the infrared spectra of the ligand and the complexes showed, in all the cases, the disappearance of the S-H band, appearing at 2560 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand. Lowering in the position of the primary alcoholic, C-O stretching frequency band from 1040 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand to 1020, 1010, 1025 and 1015 cm^{-1} in the spectra of complexes reveals that the primary alcoholic group is involved in the co-ordination. Thiovanol may, thus, be taken to be acting as a mononegative bidentate ligand, co-ordinating through the anionic sulphhydryl group and neutral primary alcoholic group.

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